

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Use of Hazardous Pesticides in Europe

On average it decreased by 15% between 2011 and 2020 for the countries considered

Eurostat calculates the use of dangerous pesticides used in the Member States. The use of pesticides involves risks and impacts on human health and the environment. The index is set at 100 as an average over the period 2015-2017.

Ranking of countries by value of hazardous pesticide use in Europe in 2020. Latvia ranks first by value of hazardous pesticide use in Europe with an amount of 134, followed by Bulgaria with an amount of 122, and Denmark with an amount of 101 units. Lithuania closes the ranking with an amount of 68, and Belgium and Luxembourg with an amount of 58.

Ranking of countries by value of the use of hazardous pesticides in Europe between 2011 and 2020. Latvia ranks first by value of the percentage change of pesticide use in Europe with an amount of 143.64% or a value equal to 79 units, followed by Lithuania with an amount of 112.5% equal to an amount of 36 units and by Hungary with an amount of 34.33% equal to an amount of 23 units. The ranking is closed by Belgium with an amount of -49.57% equal to an amount of -57 units, followed by Luxembourg with an amount of -56.72% equal to an amount of -76 units and by the Netherlands with an amount of -68.48% equal to an amount of -176 units. On average between 2011 and 2020 the value of the use of dangerous pesticides in Europe decreased from an amount of 101.31 to a value of 85.19 units or equal to a reduction of -15.92% equal to a amount of -16.13 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Specifically, three different clusters are presented, namely:

- Cluster 1: Czech Republic, Austria, Croatia, Hungary, France, Belgium, Slovakia, Ireland, Luxembourg, Romania, Slovenia, Lithuania, Latvia;
- Cluster 2: Bulgaria;
- Cluster 3: The Netherlands.

If we consider the value of the median, the following ordering results: $C2=122 > C1=81.5 > C3=81$.

Network Analysis using the Euclidean distance. A network analysis using the Euclidean distance is presented below. Two network structures are identified, one of which is complex and one is simplified.

There is a complex network structure made up of the following connections:

- The Czech Republic has a connection with Croatia amounting to 0.6 units, and with Austria amounting to 0.79 units;
- Austria has a connection with the Czech Republic in the amount of 0.79 units and with Croatia in the amount of 0.57 units;

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

- Croatia has a connection with the Czech Republic in the amount of 0.6 units and with Austria in the amount of 0.57 units.

There is a complex network structure made up of the following countries:

- Romania and Slovakia have a connection for an amount equal to a value of 0.66 units.

Conclusions. The value of the use of hazardous pesticides in Europe between 2011 and 2020 decreased on average by about 15% for the countries considered. Reducing the use of pesticides is a good thing for increasing the food safety of European agricultural products. However, there are some countries where the use of dangerous pesticides has increased, namely Romania with +30%, Slovakia with an amount of +24.66%, and Slovenia with an amount of +4.88%. The country that has most reduced the use of pesticides is Holland with -68.48% between 2011 and 2020. European agricultural economic policies are aimed at increasing organic production, local specialties, and promoting an idea of sustainable agriculture also for rural communities as well as for consumers. It must therefore be considered that the reduction of the use of dangerous pesticides is in line with the aims of European economic policies for sustainable agriculture. However, to further reduce the use of dangerous pesticides in agriculture it is possible to act with taxes that can make it inconvenient for consumers to buy products that use dangerous pesticides. This taxation could also be applied to the dangerous pesticides themselves in order to increase production costs for farms that intend to use them by squeezing their profits.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Uso dei Pesticidi Pericolosi in Europa tra il 2011 ed il 2020

